

How Dutch populists (unsuccessfully) try to exploit the Corona Virus

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The wide variety of responses to the corona crisis of populist leaders and parties in the world illustrate the different aspects of populism. Various national manifestations of populism can be identified. Trump, for example, openly questioned the expertise of his own national health institute, and added a racist element to the coronavirus by calling it a 'Chinese virus'. Bolsonaro denied the reality of the threat the virus poses, framing it as just another flue and emphasizing the importance of the economy continuing as usual.

In the Netherlands, on the other hand, the leaders of the country's two main populist parties – Thierry Baudet from Forum for Democracy (FvD) and Geert Wilders from the Party for Freedom (PVV) – both find themselves in the opposition and blamed the ruling coalition parties for not taking enough measures to fight the coronavirus. The Dutch coalition took its measures in a very gradual manner. In mid-March, when many other European countries started to close their borders (and restrict the freedom of movement of their citizens to unprecedented extents), the Netherlands didn't do so. Instead, the government called for a so-called 'intelligent lockdown', in which staying at home is not mandatory, but encouraged. Both FvD and PVV pleaded for a 'total lockdown' and protection and control over the Dutch borders (i).

According to Eelco Harteveld, a political scientist at the Universiteit van Amsterdam, such a plea is typical for nativist populists (ii). A nativist discourse underlines the 'spatial and territorial' elements of indigeneity, promoting and protecting the interest of the indigenous. Such a discourse was already remarkably visible in the Dutch context (Kaya 2019) (iii). Euroscepticism and nationalism that is part of this discourse is also demonstrated in their stances towards the EU, specifically in their attempts to thwart the Eurobonds (bonds issued jointly by the euro countries to prevent the Member States from falling over and the eurozone from collapsing) – one of the proposed solutions for helping especially Italy and Spain combat the virus and save their economies. According to the FvD and the PVV these Eurobonds will result in an unequal divide between the 'wealthy' Northern countries of the EU and the 'poor' southern countries, where the wealthy countries will end up with debts of the South. Baudet's and Wilders's opposition to the 'intelligent lockdown' and Eurobonds didn't hold for long, because the coalition party, after all, started

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to control the Dutch borders, and the EU closed its outside borders (iv). According to Hartevelde this was not particularly favourable for Dutch populists because their criticisms were adopted within a short period, and they, therefore, lost the ability to thrive on these themes and oppose the government (v).

Catherine de Vries, professor political economy of the University of Bocconi in Milan, argues in the Dutch Financial Times that it is tempting to think that populist parties will grow as a result of the corona outbreak (vi). She discusses various studies, however, showing that at a time of crisis, citizens need solutions. If governments act unanimously, and the taken measures prove effective, they can be electorally rewarded. For example, according to the latest poll in Germany, Merkel's response to the coronavirus pandemic resulted in a 7 percent increase of her party nationwide (vii). Opposition parties that criticize these measures from the side-lines can be seen as displaying political impotence. Looking at possible long-term effects, the recession that will result from the coronavirus may end up in favour of the populists, however. De Vries cites research that shows that the support for right-wing populist parties increases after an economic crisis, as right-wing populists are good at finding scapegoats to exploit an electoral crisis.

Thomas Jaeger, a political scientist from the University of Cologne, expects that the reintroduction of internal European borders will strengthen the populists (viii). He asserts that the longer the crisis will continue, the more prominent nationalism will become. In a similar vein, Philippe Legrain expects that 'especially when it reinforces other trends that are already undermining globalization', the coronavirus is likely to have a lasting impact (ix). The virus will provide political fodder, and is a political gift for protectionists and nationalists who favour greater immigration controls and protectionism, according to Legrain. It reinforces the idea that foreigners are a threat and confirms the view that countries in crisis cannot always count on their allies and neighbours.

Cas Mudde, who attempts to answer the question "Will the coronavirus kill populism?" in the Guardian is also sceptical (x). He emphasizes that populist parties show wildly varying responses to the corona threat. A lot has been written about the incompetence of Trump and Bolsonaro, but others, such as India's Narendra Modi, may be more effective in their attempts to control the outbreak. Most likely, the virus will not 'kill populism', "for the simple reason that 'populism' does not have one, unitary response to the pandemic".

The financial crisis in 2008 and the refugee crisis in 2015 have generated greater public support for populists worldwide. Whether right-wing populists in the Netherlands will electorally benefit from the coronavirus remains to be seen.

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(ii) Populisten kijken verschillend aan tegen het coronavirus hoe kan dat ?, Romana Abels, Trouw, April 2 2020, available at: <https://www.trouw.nl/buitenland/populisten-kijken-verschillend-aan-tegen-het-coronavirus-hoe-kan-dat~b495140b/>

(iii) Ayhan Kaya (2020). Populism and Heritage in Europe, lost in diversity and unity. Routledge. ISBN 9780429457678

(iv) <https://twitter.com/fvdemocratie/status/1244971379113558016>

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(vi) Kunnen rechts populistische partijen electoral munt slaan uit de corona-uitbraak? FD, March 8 2020, available at: <https://fd.nl/opinie/1336936/kunnen-rechts-populistische-partijen-electoraal-munt-slaan-uit-de-corona-uitbraak>

(vii) Merkel shines in handling of Germany's coronavirus, France 24, March 29 2020, available at: <https://www.france24.com/en/20200329-merkel-shines-in-handling-of-germany-s-coronavirus-crisis>

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(ix) The Coronavirus is killing globalization as we know it, Foreign Policy, March 12 2020, available at: <https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/03/12/coronavirus-killing-globalization-nationalism-protectionism-trump/>

(x) Will the coronavirus 'kill populism'? Don't count on it, The Guardian, March 27 2020, available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/mar/27/coronavirus-populism-trump-politics-response>

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